

Data Collection from Developers

We are conducting a research study aimed at improving the experiences, challenges, and practices of JavaScript developers. To do so, we are organizing a focus group where we will discuss various aspects related to JavaScript development. Your participation is essential to enrich our research with valuable and practical insights. Developers with knowledge of JavaScript are welcome to participate. The estimated time to complete this survey is between 1 and 4 minutes.

The Informed Consent Form is available at the link below. Please read it carefully and, after reading, fill out the form

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/14EdqCnjQoKMa7EyUpfT1y-JfIU2JzpN8Z-0WnGANjyl/edit?usp=sharing>

* Indicates required question

1. Developer's Name *

2. E-mail *

3. Contact Number (Whatsapp) *

4. Position *

Mark only one oval.

Frontend Developer

Backend Developer

Fullstack Developer

QA Developer

Other

5. Years of experience with JavaScript *

Mark only one oval.

- 1 ~ 2 years
- 3 ~ 4 years
- 5 ~ 10 years
- No Experience

6. Years of experience with unit testing in JavaScript *

Mark only one oval.

- 1 ~ 2 years
- 3 ~ 4 years
- 5 ~ 10 years
- No Experience

7. Would you be able to attend a meeting? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

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